

“DEVELOPMENT OF A MARKETING STRATEGY USING THE EXAMPLE OF A CONFECTIONERY FACTORY”

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Abstract: Enterprise strategy is the development of marketing strategies. The development of marketing strategies is considered as a key stage in the strategic planning process of the enterprise as a whole and is a necessary element to achieve the best results of the company's activities.

Key words: Marketing strategy, confectionery, products, market, trademark.

Introduction: for large companies with large assets, capital-intensive production, and a large production structure, the presence of a development strategy is considered simply a necessary condition for survival. It is strategic planning that allows a company to determine its goals and what it needs to strive for, through which to develop its business or simply survive in increasing competition.

Results: Today in the market, large companies that apply strategic planning and have a well-developed and transparent development strategy have achieved success in their activities. But even when achieving success, for the sake of its continued existence, the company must resort to strategic planning. This should not be a one-time process, but an ongoing, ongoing activity of top managers. The use of strategy as a management tool in the daily activities of a company is a necessary condition and means of not only survival, but also ensuring the prosperity of the company.

One of the main points of enterprise strategies is the development of marketing strategies. The development of marketing strategies is considered as a key stage in the strategic planning process of the enterprise as a whole and is a necessary element to achieve the best results of the company's activities.

Recently, marketing strategies have become increasingly important. Just a few years ago, strategic marketing was presented primarily as determining the general direction of a company's activities, oriented toward the future and responding to changing external conditions. Recently, the main emphasis has been on the formation of a market-oriented effective organizational and management system and the allocation in accordance with these management resources.

The essence of marketing in the modern consumer market is the priority of individual needs overall production and commercial activities of the enterprise. Therefore, marketing should be considered not only as one of the management elements, but also as a global function that determines the content of all production and marketing activities of the enterprise. As a result, modern marketing becomes, first of all, strategic, the focus and scientific validity of marketing decisions is increasing, short-term plans are increasingly based on long-term programs that determine the global goals of the enterprise in the market. The goal is to develop elements of a marketing strategy for a confectionery factory.

This work is based on research conducted by the author regarding the assessment of the potential of the confectionery market, analysis of the competitive environment, marketing strategies of competitors, the position of their brands in the market, as well as the identification of target market segments to which a certain brand will be aimed. Taking into account the results of these studies, a strategy for segmentation, positioning and branding was developed, and specific measures for the implementation of these strategies, included in the marketing-mix complex, were proposed.

At this point in time, according to experts, the increase in prices for sweet products are not expected. At the confectionery market you can see a lot of beautiful and original decorated products, which attracts more and more consumers. Knowing Manufacturers skillfully take advantage of this, wrapping their products in beautiful, bright packaging to further attract consumers. Confectionery products have become so firmly established in the diet that it is impossible not to consider them an important food product. Therefore, manufacturers face One of the important tasks is to constantly improve the quality of confectionery products.

Recently, many factories, combines, bakeries for the production of confectionery products. Most of products are supplied to the regions where the enterprises are located. All changes occurring in the external environment, by analogy push for the need to adopt new management principles production.

Each change presents complex economic and social system, but production must be adapted to fast and effective change in external factors and must withstand them influence. In the confectionery market, competitors are watching everyone a mistake of one or another competitor [2]. In the modern world, this problem can be solved by a set of measures, components of enterprise marketing research.

Today, marketing research is especially relevant because they allow us to develop methods for targeted regulation of production, with prospects for the development of consumer demand. The complexity of this process is caused only by the specifics of market relations in this area, features of pricing and strategic assortment planning and the nature of processes of new types products. Many enterprises purchase foreign equipment, which allows you to expand the range and improve the quality of products.

Marketing research is about identifying suitable products, services and markets to which they can be offered to them. Analysis of the external environment is a key aspect when creating marketing research in which the organization operates, since changes in this environment can lead to both expansion marketing opportunities and to limit the scope.

Marketing research is being developed to expand sales and market development to increase profits and improve image among competing manufacturers, for consumer recognition. At When using marketing research, an enterprise should consider:

- a) demand development trend;
- b) the state and features of competition in the market, the main competitors and areas of their activity;
- c) managerial resources and capabilities of the company;
- d) basic concepts of company development (conducting oral, written surveys, surveys).

“Confil” enterprise aims to organize a geographically separate production, enter the market with a new name and introduce a new trademark “Biosladiya”, the product range of which includes about three hundred items. Cookies, muffins, waffles, candies and much more are the excellent result of the work of specialists in the confectionery industry, based on environmentally friendly domestic raw materials.

All products are created on the basis of natural raw materials. Thanks to a carefully selected composition of ingredients, the products have a balanced, delicate taste and pleasant aroma. The company is constantly improving the production technology of all types of products, updating the range, creating new shades of aroma and taste to satisfy the needs of every customer.

Quality control is carried out at all stages of production by our own laboratory, the equipment of which allows us to obtain objective data on the quality of products. All products comply with the requirements of current standards, which is confirmed by hygiene certificates and certificates of conformity.

Every day, the company's specialists (designers and marketers) work to improve the quality and appearance of packaging. They developed and protected original exclusive packaging - special plastic containers with a brand name.

Today the company is one of the largest manufacturers of confectionery products in the region and supplies its products to regions of Russia and the CIS countries. The company's assortment includes more than 300 types of excellent confectionery products, including about 30 types - marmalade, marshmallows, marshmallows and Turkish delight. A wide range of high-quality products has received consumer recognition. “Biosladiya” trademark covers a significant share of the confectionery market and is becoming a national brand.

Conclusion: In accordance with the data presented, there is a high level of competition among confectionery manufacturers. There has been a tendency towards an increase in the volume of production and sales of confectionery products by competing factories, a fierce struggle for the existing market. When compared with competitors, it turned out that their products look better in quality and range, but not by much. It is possible to compete only on price (by reducing it).

As a result of considering the contact environment, the following conclusions can be drawn, which can later be used to determine the potential opportunities and threats in the immediate environment of the organization. The contact environment of the organization in question contains more threats than opportunities, among which the following can be distinguished:

- influence of suppliers and consumers,
- increased pressure from competitors,
- high concentration of production and level of competition.

As for the possibilities, the main ones are:

- wide popularity in the region,
- entering new markets,
- development of the confectionery industry.

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